

Naturkompass Citizen Science Data Model

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Document note: This document is a methodological report. It is not a peer-reviewed journal article and does not present final empirical results.

Abstract

Naturkompass is a biodiversity knowledge, education and participation platform for private gardens, urban green spaces and small-scale habitat mosaics. Its citizen-science layer is designed to make voluntary biodiversity observations and habitat-related garden information methodologically usable without exposing exact private-garden locations or publishing raw personal data. This report documents the current public-facing citizen-science data model of Naturkompass as of 25 May 2026.

The model combines garden context, habitat modules, plant inventory entries, observation records, user-controlled consent states, spatial generalisation and aggregation thresholds. It is explicitly designed for low-threshold participation rather than official monitoring. Contributions are therefore interpreted as voluntary, heterogeneous and bias-prone observational inputs that can support pattern detection, educational use and possible future aggregated Open-Data outputs (subject to governance review), but not authoritative single-record biodiversity evidence.

The report defines the conceptual objects, observation classes, quality flags, aggregation logic and interoperability direction of the system. It also describes the key limitations of the model, including sampling bias, identification uncertainty, incomplete temporal coverage and the absence of a representative sampling design. The goal is to provide a transparent and citable methodological baseline for future iterations, DOI-linked documentation and possible later dataset publication under privacy-preserving conditions.

Deutsche Zusammenfassung

Naturkompass ist eine Plattform für Biodiversitätswissen, Umweltbildung und freiwillige Beteiligung in privaten Gärten und urbanen Grünräumen. Dieses Dokument beschreibt das methodische Citizen-Science-Datenmodell der Plattform in einer zitierfähigen, transparenten Form. Im Mittelpunkt stehen freiwillige Gartenangaben, Habitatmodule, Pflanzeninventare, Tier- und Pflanzenbeobachtungen sowie datenschutzorientierte Aggregationslogiken.

Das Datenmodell ist ausdrücklich kein amtliches Monitoringmodell. Es dient dazu, freiwillige, heterogene und potenziell fehleranfällige Beobachtungen so zu strukturieren, dass spätere aggregierte Auswertungen, Bildungsanwendungen und methodisch vorsichtige Open-Data-Freigaben möglich werden. Einzelbeobachtungen gelten dabei nicht automatisch als harte wissenschaftliche Nachweise.

Dokumentiert werden die zentralen Datenobjekte, Beobachtungstypen, Qualitätsannahmen, Aggregationsschwellen, Interoperabilitätsziele und Grenzen des Modells. Das Papier bildet damit die methodische Grundlage für spätere Versionen, DOI-Veröffentlichungen und eine mögliche Weiterentwicklung zu standardisierteren Erhebungsformaten.

1. Background and rationale

Private gardens, school gardens, courtyards, balconies and other small green spaces can contribute to habitat provision, environmental learning and ecological connectivity. At the same time, they are methodologically difficult environments for biodiversity data collection. They are privately managed, highly heterogeneous, seasonally dynamic and unevenly distributed across social and geographic contexts. Most garden-related biodiversity information is therefore either informal, not easily reusable or not documented in a way that supports transparent interpretation.

Naturkompass addresses this gap by combining biodiversity information, practical habitat guidance and a voluntary citizen-science layer. The goal of the citizen-science layer is not to replicate formal monitoring schemes. Instead, the goal is to create a privacy-conscious data structure through which recurring patterns in garden biodiversity measures and observations can become visible over time.

Three design requirements shaped the model:

1. Low threshold participation: users should be able to contribute without specialist training.
2. Privacy-conscious structure: exact private-garden locations and personal identifiers should not be needed for public analysis.
3. Methodological transparency: the system should make clear what the data can and cannot support.

2. Scope of the data model

The Naturkompass citizen-science data model is a public methodological model, not a one-to-one dump of internal storage structures. It documents the conceptual objects that define how voluntary garden-related observations can be collected, linked, interpreted and, where appropriate, aggregated.

The model currently supports four broad use cases:

- personal garden documentation by registered users
- optional participation in citizen-science style aggregation
- community-level visualisation under explicit opt-in and privacy thresholds
- future publication of aggregated outputs as Open Data

The model does not support the following claims or uses:

- official biodiversity monitoring
- regulatory species records
- exact private-site occurrence publication
- evidence-grade verification of every single user entry
- inferential statements about national representativeness

3. Design principles

The data model is based on the following principles.

3.1 Voluntariness

Participation in any public-benefit or citizen-science use is voluntary. Naturkompass distinguishes between normal platform use and optional consent-based inclusion in scientific or public aggregation contexts.

3.2 Data minimisation

The public methodological model avoids dependence on exact addresses, full postal codes and exact coordinates of private gardens. Public outputs are based on coarse spatial generalisation and thresholded aggregation.

3.3 Interpretive humility

User-submitted records are valuable, but they are heterogeneous. The model therefore assumes varying levels of taxonomic certainty, effort intensity and temporal completeness.

3.4 Versionability

The model is intended to evolve. Each DOI release should therefore be versioned, citable and explicit about scope changes.

4. Core conceptual objects

The current Naturkompass citizen-science data model consists of the following conceptual objects.

4.1 Garden

A Garden is the primary contextual unit for participation. It represents a private or semi-private green-space context associated with one user account. In the current repository state, garden-level context includes attributes such as:

- garden type
- approximate total area
- sealed area share
- conventional lawn share
- exposition
- creation time

The garden is not treated as a publicly exposed location entity. It acts as the internal anchor for consent, module linkage and observation linkage.

4.2 Consent state

A Consent state controls whether a garden may be used for citizen-science aggregation. The reviewed codebase distinguishes between garden-level citizen-science consent and profile-level public community visibility. These must be interpreted separately.

Relevant conceptual properties are:

- consent granted / revoked state
- consent timestamp
- consent document version
- revocation timestamp
- consent audit trail in legal consent records

4.3 Garden module

A Garden module represents a habitat or structural intervention, such as deadwood, pond structure, sand habitat, hedge element or other nature-garden component. The module object allows Naturkompass to analyse implemented habitat structures, not only species sightings.

Relevant properties include:

- module type
- size category
- balcony flag or small-space suitability
- optional area estimate
- optional notes
- timestamp of addition

4.4 Plant record

A Plant record represents the presence of a plant in a user's documented garden inventory. This is conceptually distinct from a one-time observation. Inventory records are useful for describing planting composition, habitat potential and possible later links to ecological interactions.

Relevant properties include:

- species reference
- source or import pathway
- optional original name
- optional observation date
- optional quantity
- optional confidence value for taxonomic matching

4.5 Observation record

An Observation record represents an event-like or diary-style entry, such as an animal sighting, a plant observation or a phenological event. Current observation structures include species name, species type, date and optional note fields.

Relevant properties include:

- species type
- species identifier where available
- species name text
- observation date
- optional note

Weather context and media linkage are not part of the current observation schema. These may be considered as extensions in future model versions.

4.6 Photo-assisted identification

A Photo-assisted identification represents an AI-supported suggestion workflow, not a final authoritative identification. It is conceptually separate from the observation record itself.

Relevant properties include:

- source model or tool
- up to several proposed taxa
- confidence score (NUMERIC 0.0-1.0, stored per species-catalogue match)
- user acceptance through submission (explicit confirmation/rejection logging is planned but not yet implemented)
- matching against the Naturkompass species catalogue

Note: a photo-AI suggestion is never automatically promoted to an expert-verified record. The confidence value reflects catalogue-matching quality, not photo-model certainty. No observation is marked as `expert_verified` based solely on an AI suggestion.

4.7 Quality and aggregation state

A Quality and aggregation state determines whether records remain private, become eligible for internal aggregation or contribute to public outputs.

Relevant properties include:

- quality flags
- sensitivity handling level
- aggregation eligibility
- minimum cell-size threshold outcome
- public visibility status

4.8 Data object summary table

The following table summarises the core objects, their implementation basis, public exposure status and associated risk dimensions.

Object	DB basis	Publicly exposed?	Privacy risk	Quality risk
Garden	gardens table	No - internal anchor only	Low (no address stored publicly)	Low
Consent state	gardens.cs_consent_version, legal_consent	No - internal audit log	Low	Low
Garden module	garden_modules table	Aggregated counts only (min. cell size ≥ 5)	Low	Low-Medium
Plant record	plant_diary / inventory tables	Not in public outputs	Low	Medium (user-submitted taxonomy)
Observation record	garden_observations table	Aggregated by PLZ2 + month, $k \geq 5$ distinct observers	Medium (mitigated by PLZ2 + k-floor)	Medium-High (self-reported)
Photo-assisted ID	AI suggestion workflow	Never as raw record	Low	High (AI suggestion only)
Quality / agg. state	Flags + sensitive_location_handling	Determines eligibility, not exposed directly	Low	Low

5. Observation classes supported by the model

The model currently supports or anticipates the following observation classes.

5.1 Species presence in garden inventory

This covers plants intentionally documented as part of a garden composition or species inventory.

5.2 Wildlife sightings

This covers user-reported animal observations in gardens or adjacent small green spaces.

5.3 Phenological records

This includes observations such as flowering periods or seasonally visible ecological events.

5.4 Habitat implementation records

This includes the creation or presence of structural habitat modules such as wildflower areas, deadwood elements or pond-related structures.

5.5 Standardised garden checks

The data model is compatible with future standardised garden-check workflows, but such workflows should be documented as later extensions rather than as fully mature current implementation.

6. Spatial and temporal generalisation

6.1 Spatial generalisation

The public model is designed around coarse spatial representation. In the reviewed repository state, public community logic uses two-digit postal-code prefixes, while earlier citizen-science SQL artefacts also document coarse regional outputs. Exact private addresses and exact GPS coordinates are excluded from the public methodological model.

Spatial generalisation serves three purposes:

- reducing disclosure risk for private gardens
- reducing re-identification risk for unusual records
- shifting interpretation from point records to coarse regional pattern signals

6.2 Temporal generalisation

Where outputs are aggregated, month-level grouping is preferred over exact timestamps. This reduces identifiability and aligns better with seasonal ecological interpretation.

7. Data quality model

The Naturkompass citizen-science data model treats data quality as graded rather than binary.

7.1 What the model assumes

The model assumes that contributions may differ in:

- taxonomic certainty
- observation effort

- temporal regularity
- completeness of garden documentation
- correctness of user interpretation

7.2 What the model does not assume

The model does not assume that:

- every observation is expert-verified
- every AI suggestion is correct
- every garden is documented systematically
- every region is represented equally
- every absence means true ecological absence

7.3 Aggregation thresholds and k-anonymity parameters

The following threshold values are implemented in the current system and govern when aggregated outputs are computed and released. These values are configurable via environment variables and may be adjusted as the dataset grows.

Parameter	Default value	Purpose
CS_MIN_GARDENS	500	Minimum number of participating gardens before any aggregated public output is generated. Below this threshold, the system operates in teaser mode with no data output.
CS_MIN_CELL_SIZE	5	Minimum number of gardens per aggregation cell (garden type, module type, observation month). Cells below this threshold are suppressed.
k-anonymity floor	5 distinct observers	Community heatmap outputs require at least 5 distinct user accounts per PLZ2 region. Regions below this floor are excluded from heatmap outputs entirely.
Spatial unit	PLZ2 (two-digit postal code prefix)	Finest spatial resolution for any public output. Exact postal codes and GPS coordinates are never included in public outputs.
Temporal unit	Calendar month	Finest temporal resolution for observation aggregates. Exact timestamps are not published.

These thresholds apply to all public-facing aggregate functions (`cs_aggregate_garden_types`, `cs_aggregate_modules`, `cs_aggregate_observations_by_month`) and the community heatmap view.

7.4 Quality-relevant signals

The conceptual quality layer may draw on:

- user acceptance through submission
- source and import provenance
- matching confidence in inventory imports
- internal sensitivity flags
- image plausibility metadata markers
- aggregation threshold outcomes

8. Data release logic

The model separates several layers of data handling.

8.1 Platform data

These are internal operational records used to provide user-facing platform functionality.

8.2 User contributions

These include inventories, habitat modules and observations submitted within the user account context.

8.3 Aggregated citizen-science outputs

These are thresholded, generalised outputs derived from eligible contributions.

8.4 Public Open-Data outputs

Public Open-Data release is a future governance objective. No such release is currently active or scheduled. Any future release would require:

- explicit consent from all contributing users
- verified satisfaction of aggregation thresholds (see Section 7.3)
- sensitive taxon review
- a dedicated governance decision and version update of this document

The current model supports aggregated release logic as a technical foundation, not unrestricted raw-record publication. Community-facing heatmap outputs (PLZ2-level, $k \geq 5$) represent the current ceiling of public data exposure.

9. Interoperability outlook

Naturkompass should be understood as interoperable in orientation, but selective in release practice.

9.1 Darwin Core compatibility thinking

For species-related observations, a later mapping to Darwin Core style structures is possible at the level of conceptual fields such as taxon, date, occurrence context and generalised locality. However, raw direct exports should not be assumed without additional quality and privacy review.

9.2 DataCite and Zenodo

The documentation and any later datasets should use formal metadata, versioning and DOI-based citation practices, making them stable and traceable over time.

9.3 GBIF-compatible mindset, not automatic GBIF publication

Naturkompass may use biodiversity informatics concepts that are broadly compatible with later integration work, but the current model does not justify direct publication of raw user-contributed observations into GBIF-style infrastructures without further validation and risk controls.

10. Limitations

This section is essential to the integrity of the model.

10.1 Sampling bias

Participants are self-selected. The data therefore likely overrepresent digitally active, biodiversity-interested users with access to gardens or garden-like spaces.

10.2 Urban-rural and ownership bias

Private-garden participation differs strongly across housing forms, ownership patterns and socio-economic contexts.

10.3 Identification bias

Species identification may be incorrect, especially in insect-rich or morphologically difficult groups.

10.4 Seasonal incompleteness

Many users will document only certain periods, visible flowering peaks or memorable sightings.

10.5 No representative random sampling

The model does not produce a random or stratified sample of gardens and should not be interpreted as nationally representative survey infrastructure.

10.6 No authoritative single-record evidence

Individual observations should not be treated as regulatory or conservation-proof evidence without additional review.

10.7 Sensitive taxon and location handling

Certain taxa carry elevated risk if their occurrence locations become publicly accessible. This includes species vulnerable to disturbance, collection pressure or persecution (e.g. rare orchids, bat roosts, reptile populations, nest sites of protected birds).

The Naturkompass data model implements a four-level sensitivity classification for all taxa in the species catalogue, stored in the `sensitive_location_handling` field on both the plants and animals tables:

Level	Value	Behaviour
Standard	standard	Normal aggregation and PLZ2-level heatmap inclusion
Aggregate only	aggregate_only	Included in counts and module aggregates; excluded from species-named outputs
Coarse region only	coarse_region_only	Only coarse regional (country/NUTS2) visibility; no PLZ2 output
Hidden	hidden	Excluded from all public outputs regardless of aggregation level

This classification is applied at the species-catalogue level, not at the individual observation level, and does not override user consent settings. It acts as an additional safeguard layer on top of the k-anonymity floor and spatial generalisation described in Section 7.3.

11. Implementation-informed status statement

The repository state reviewed on 25 May 2026 shows that Naturkompass already contains real implementation foundations for this model, including:

- garden-level contextual records
- garden-module records
- observation records

- legal consent logging
- threshold-based citizen-science aggregate functions
- privacy-conscious public visibility settings

At the same time, this report intentionally documents the model at the methodological level. It does not claim that every operational workflow is already final, automated or empirically validated.

12. Versioning and future development

Version 1.1.0 is the current citable baseline of the Naturkompass citizen-science data model. Version 1.0.0 (25 May 2026) remains the initial baseline and is superseded by this version. Future versions may extend the model in areas such as:

- richer phenology categories
- standardised observation protocols
- explicit quality-tier labels
- sensitivity-aware taxon handling
- multilingual field harmonisation
- export schemas for approved aggregated datasets

Each future version should clearly state which parts are:

- already implemented
- pilot-stage
- planned but not yet operational

13. Conclusion

The Naturkompass citizen-science data model is designed to support a middle path between informal garden note-taking and formal biodiversity monitoring. It provides enough structure for aggregation, interpretation and future Open-Science documentation, while remaining explicit about uncertainty, privacy limits and methodological constraints.

Its core value lies not in pretending that garden observations are automatically authoritative, but in making voluntary everyday biodiversity documentation structured, privacy-conscious, interpretable and citable.

References and source basis

Internal implementation sources

This report is based on a repository audit of the Naturkompass codebase and database migrations reviewed on 25 May 2026 and updated on 3 June 2026, including in particular:

- frontend/supabase/migrations/20260524b_fix_security_linter.sql
- frontend/supabase/migrations/20260525a_privacy_governance.sql - EXIF/GPS removal, sensitive_location_handling, source_registry
- frontend/supabase/migrations/phase4_community_heatmap_v2_privacy.sql - k-anonymity floor (k=5), PLZ2 aggregation
- create_cs_anonymized_views.sql

- `add_garden_observations.sql`
- `frontend/migrations/add_garden_modules.sql`
- `frontend/migrations/add_gardens_and_certifications.sql`
- `frontend/src/lib/citizen-science-config.ts` - CS_MIN_GARDENS, CS_MIN_CELL_SIZE defaults
- `frontend/src/app/api/cs-aggregates/route.ts`

External references

The following external sources provide methodological context for the design decisions described in this report.

Citizen Science methodology and bias: - Pocock, M.J.O., Chapman, D.S., Sheppard, L.J. & Roy, H.E. (2014). Choosing and Using Citizen Science: a guide to when and how to use citizen science to monitor biodiversity and the environment. NERC Centre for Ecology & Hydrology. - Silvertown, J. (2009). A new dawn for citizen science. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*, 24(9), 467-471. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2009.03.017> - Isaac, N.J.B. et al. (2014). Statistics for citizen science: extracting signals from noisy and biased data. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*, 5(10), 1052-1060. <https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.12254>

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Biodiversity informatics standards: - Wieczorek, J. et al. (2012). Darwin Core: An Evolving Community-Developed Biodiversity Data Standard. *PLOS ONE*, 7(1), e29715. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0029715> - DataCite Metadata Working Group (2021). DataCite Metadata Schema Documentation for the Publication and Citation of Research Data and Other Research Outputs. Version 4.4. <https://doi.org/10.14454/3w3z-sa82> - GBIF Secretariat (2021). GBIF Data Quality Requirements. <https://www.gbif.org/data-quality-requirements>

k-Anonymity: - Sweeney, L. (2002). k-anonymity: A model for protecting privacy. *International Journal of Uncertainty, Fuzziness and Knowledge-Based Systems*, 10(5), 557-570. <https://doi.org/10.1142/S0218488502001648>